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2 **The recent and future PM_{2.5}-related health burden in**
3 **China apportioned by emission source**

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22 **Abstract:** This study estimated PM_{2.5} (atmospheric fine particulate matter with aerodynamic
23 diameter $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{g}$) concentrations and the health burden in mainland China from 2010 to 2049 under
24 two scenarios: Current Legislations and Maximum Technical Feasible Reductions. We assess
25 premature deaths from PM_{2.5} exposure, examining sources like coal combustion, biomass burning,
26 industry, and tailpipe emission from on-road transport. Results show that central and eastern China
27 account for 75% of PM_{2.5}-related deaths, with biomass burning (40%) and industry (34%) as
28 primary contributors. Under the Current Legislations and Maximum Technical Feasible Reductions
29 scenarios, PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths are projected to decrease by 43% and 80% (linear EVA)
30 and by 28% increase and 40% decrease (nonlinear EVA) from 2010 to 2049. Assuming a linear
31 relationship, the Maximum Technical Feasible Reductions scenario estimates that reduced PM_{2.5}
32 exposure could avoid 1.55 million premature deaths annually by 2049 compared to 2010, primarily
33 from coal combustion for heating, biomass burning, industry, and tailpipe emission from on-road
34 transport.
35

36 Main

37 With the rapid development of urbanization and industrialization, PM_{2.5} (atmospheric fine
38 particulate matter with aerodynamic diameter $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{g}$) pollution remains one of the major
39 environmental problems facing China. As reported in the 2022 China Ecological and Environmental
40 Conditions Bulletin¹, 126 cities in China have exceeded ambient air quality standards (HJ 663-2013;
41 Annual average PM_{2.5} concentration limit of $35 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, Daily average PM_{2.5} concentration limit of
42 $75 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)². Among them, the number of days with PM_{2.5} exceeding the standard is particularly
43 serious, accounting for 36.9% of the total number of days with exceeding the standard. Meanwhile,
44 PM_{2.5} poses a serious threat to human health³. According to the new state of global air report for
45 2024, in 2021, it has been estimated that 8.1 million people worldwide died due to indoor and
46 outdoor air pollution^{4,5}. The majority of these premature deaths occur in urban areas, where more
47 than 50% of the global population—over 3.5 billion people—currently resides. According to the
48 World Urbanization Prospects⁶, this figure is expected to rise to 70% by 2050 urbanization
49 continues⁷. China, as one of the countries with a large population and high levels of air pollution,
50 faces Dietary risk factors, high blood pressure, tobacco exposure, and ambient particulate matter
51 pollution as the leading risk factor for premature death among its residents⁸. Previous research⁹
52 reported that in 2013, stroke, ischemic heart disease (IHD), lung cancer (LC), and chronic
53 obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) caused by air pollution accounted for 50%, 28%, 9%, and
54 12% of the total premature mortality in China, respectively. In response, China has implemented a
55 series of air pollution control measures, such as the "Action Plan for the Battle Against Heavy
56 Pollution Weather, Ozone Pollution Prevention and Control, and Diesel Truck Pollution
57 Treatment"¹⁰, and the "Carbon Peak and Carbon Neutrality Goals"¹¹, which have significantly

58 reduced PM_{2.5} concentrations. However, according to the Global Burden of Disease 2019
59 comparative risk assessment, ambient PM_{2.5} pollution still led to approximately 1.4 million
60 premature deaths in China in 2019¹². Luo et al. similarly reported that shipping-related PM_{2.5}
61 declined in all Chinese port cities under controls on sulfur emissions from shipping. However, the
62 nationwide mortality rate from shipping-related, long-term exposure to PM_{2.5} increased by 11.4%,
63 reaching 48,300 deaths by 2020¹³. To address this issue, China has made further efforts to improve
64 air quality, and significant changes in future PM_{2.5} pollution levels and the associated health burden
65 are anticipated. There is an urgent need for a quantitative assessment of the current and future health
66 burden attributable to PM_{2.5} in China, which will be critical in informing the design of future air
67 quality policies.

68 In health impact assessment models, the relationship between PM_{2.5} pollution and mortality is
69 represented by exposure-response functions (ERFs)¹⁴. Traditionally, this relationship has been
70 considered linear¹⁵⁻¹⁷. However, recent studies^{18,19} suggest that the ERFs for PM_{2.5} exposure and
71 mortality may be nonlinear, with a steeper increase in the impacts at lower concentrations than at
72 higher concentrations. Comparing the health burdens attributable to PM_{2.5} based on linear versus
73 nonlinear ERFs provides potential insights into effectively avoiding premature deaths due to PM_{2.5}
74 exposure. It also offers opportunities for enhancing regulatory capabilities, which may be a
75 prerequisite for implementing more stringent measures.

76 Furthermore, mitigating the health impacts of PM_{2.5} pollution requires identifying the relative
77 importance of various emission sources. Existing studies²⁰⁻²⁴ indicate that anthropogenic emission
78 sources, including coal combustion, biomass burning, vehicular emissions, and industrial sources,
79 are the predominant source categories across most regions of China under both historical and future

80 business-as-usual scenarios. Anenberg et al. estimated the contribution of global transportation
81 tailpipe emissions to the health burden associated with ambient PM_{2.5} in 2010 and 2015 using the
82 GEOS-Chem model and epidemiological health impact assessment methods and reported that
83 transportation emissions accounted for approximately 11.7% of global PM_{2.5}- and ozone- related
84 deaths in 2010 and 11.4% in 2015²⁵. Reddington et al. explored the health benefits of eliminating
85 emissions from different anthropogenic sources in South and East Asia in 2014 using the WRF-
86 Chem model. They found that removing residential or industrial emissions could avoid 0.47 (95%
87 confidence interval [CI]: 0.41-0.54) or 0.28 (95% CI: 0.236-0.36) million premature deaths annually,
88 respectively, in India, China, and Southeast Asia²⁶. Conibear et al. estimated the impact of future
89 emission scenarios on air pollution exposure in China using the emulators, which were machine
90 learning models trained and tested on simulator data from WRF-Chem. They found that, compared
91 to the Current Legislation Emission (CLE) scenario in 2050, the application of the best air pollution
92 technologies provides substantial health benefits, reducing the PM_{2.5}-related health burden by 16%,
93 avoiding 0.54 (95% CI: 0.5-0.57) million premature deaths per year. These public health benefits
94 are mainly due to reductions in industrial (43%) and residential (30%) emissions²⁷. Based on the
95 WRF-Chem model and the Global Exposure Mortality Model (GEMM), Shen et al. assessed the
96 impact of rural Chinese residential emissions on PM_{2.5} and health. They found that transitioning to
97 clean energy significantly reduced contributions to ambient PM_{2.5}, avoiding 0.13 (0.09-0.16) million
98 premature deaths due to PM_{2.5} exposure. The climate forcing associated with this sector declines
99 from 0.057 ± 0.016 W/m² in 1992 to 0.031 ± 0.008 W/m² in 2012²⁸. Guo et al. evaluated the health
100 benefits of air quality improvements following the deployment of clean energy in Hebei Province,
101 China. They found that the pollutant emissions for 2030 could be reduced by 18-45% and 33-66%

102 under the General Policy and Strengthened Policy scenarios, with the residential sector contributing
103 the most. The General Policy scenario presented the moderate target of clean energy substitution,
104 taking into account the economic feasibility and applicability of options and measures, while the
105 Strengthened Policy scenario showed the ambitious target of clean energy deployment, which means
106 the maximum potential to use clean energy in the energy-consuming sectors. Correspondingly, the
107 health burden related to air pollution in 2030 would be reduced by 7,499 and 12,260 cases,
108 respectively, under these scenarios²⁹.

109 In summary, the aforementioned studies demonstrate the significant benefits of controlling
110 emissions from PM_{2.5} sources on air quality improvement and human health. However, previous
111 research has mostly focused on the environmental health benefits of historical or future emission
112 scenarios or has concentrated on specific regions within China. Few studies have considered (1) the
113 contributions of various emission sources to the health burden in China over a long-term period
114 from the past to future periods, and (2) the impacts of PM_{2.5} exposure-induced health benefits under
115 nonlinear and linear relationships. Therefore, such studies are urgently needed to understand the
116 extent to which different future scenarios will lead to improvements in air quality and health in
117 China relative to the historical period, the extent to which specific emitting sources will contribute,
118 and how the use of health impact assessment models for linear and nonlinear relationships affects
119 the estimation of health burdens.

120 To address these issues, using the Danish Eulerian Hemispheric Model (DEHM) and the Economic
121 Valuation of Air pollution (EVA) model, this study (1) estimated the number of premature deaths
122 associated with PM_{2.5} pollution in mainland China during the historical period (2010-2014) and
123 future periods (2020-2049) under CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE (based on CESM_SSP2-4.5

124 meteorological data and Current Legislation Emission Scenario (CLE) emission assumptions) and
125 CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR (based on CESM_SSP1-2.6 meteorological data and Maximum Feasible
126 Reductions (MFR) emission assumptions) scenario assumptions; (2) compared the impact of linear
127 relationships (World Health Organization recommends a relative risk of 8.0%, referred to as
128 WHO_RR) and nonlinear relationships on the health burden, explored the spatial distribution
129 characteristics of PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths, and quantified the impact of specific
130 anthropogenic emission sources (coal combustion, biomass burning, industrial and transportation
131 sources) on PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths, thereby identifying their primary sources. This
132 comprehensive study provides detailed source information necessary for prioritizing PM_{2.5} air
133 pollution control and reducing health risks associated with PM_{2.5}.

134

135 **Results**

136 **Future PM_{2.5} concentrations and population projections**

137 Figure 1(a) shows the projected changes in the total population size of China from 2010 to 2049 and
138 the changes in the annual mean PM_{2.5} concentration changes under the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE
139 scenario and CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario. Figure 1(b) shows the age distributions in China
140 from 2010 to 2049. The predicted PM_{2.5} concentrations and population sizes will serve as the basis
141 for subsequent research to better assess China's environmental health impacts. From Figure 1(a), it
142 can be found that the total population size is expected to peak at 1.45 billion in 2020, and the trend
143 of the predicted results in this work is comparable to those of Wang et al.³⁰ and Wang et al.³¹, with
144 a maximum difference of 7%. Figure 1(b) illustrates the projected increase in the proportion of the
145 population aged 65+ from 8% in 2010 to 23% in 2049, an increase of about 170 million. Compared

146 to 2020, the population of persons aged 65 years or older in 2049 will increase by about 110 million.
 147 Additionally, this study forecasts that $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations under both scenarios will show a
 148 declining trend to varying degrees starting from 2010. Under the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario,
 149 $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations are expected to decrease by $6.7 \mu g m^{-3}$, approximately 34%, from 2010 to 2049.
 150 In contrast, the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario predicts a more significant reduction in $PM_{2.5}$
 151 concentrations by $15.3 \mu g m^{-3}$, approximately 78% (see details in Liu et al.³²).

152
 153 **Figure 1. Projection of annual average $PM_{2.5}$ concentration population sizes and age**
 154 **distributions in China from 2010 to 2049.**

155 Health burden analysis

156 Acute deaths, chronic deaths, and total deaths attributable to $PM_{2.5}$ pollution were estimated based
 157 on the linear EVA (WHO_RR), and $PM_{2.5}$ -related cause-specific deaths were estimated using the
 158 nonlinear EVA, including lung cancer, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, ischemic heart
 159 disease, stroke, lower respiratory infections, and and the sum of these as the total deaths. Detailed
 160 $PM_{2.5}$ pollutant-related causes of death in mainland China under different scenarios are summarized
 161 in Table 1. Figure 2 depicts the estimates of premature deaths related to $PM_{2.5}$ in mainland China
 162 from 2010 to 2049 under different scenarios based on linear EVA (WHO_RR) and nonlinear EVA,
 163 along with their percentage changes relative to 2010.

164 **Table 1. Premature deaths attributable to PM_{2.5} pollutants in mainland China under different**
 165 **scenarios (in million)**

Model	Premature deaths (million)	HIST	CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE					CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR			
		_CESM 2010	2020	2030	2040	2049	2020	2030	2040	2049	
Linear EVA	AD	0.37	0.32	0.21	0.19	0.18	0.32	0.10	0.07	0.06	
	CD	3.08	2.96	2.02	1.87	1.80	2.97	0.97	0.71	0.63	
	Total deaths	3.45	3.28	2.23	2.06	1.98	3.29	1.07	0.78	0.69	
Non- linear EVA	LC	0.17	0.22	0.19	0.22	0.23	0.23	0.10	0.09	0.09	
	COPD	0.29	0.29	0.26	0.33	0.34	0.29	0.14	0.14	0.14	
	IHD	0.47	0.60	0.54	0.65	0.67	0.60	0.34	0.34	0.33	
	stroke	0.15	0.18	0.15	0.19	0.19	0.18	0.07	0.07	0.06	
	LRI	0.07	0.09	0.08	0.10	0.11	0.09	0.04	0.04	0.04	
	Total deaths	1.75	2.11	1.78	2.15	2.23	2.12	1.07	1.08	1.05	

*Note: AD corresponds to acute deaths due to short-term exposures, CD to chronic deaths due to long-term exposures, LC to lung cancer, COPD to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, IHD to ischemic heart disease, and LRI corresponds to lower respiratory infections.

166 PM_{2.5} pollution-related causes of death, including AD (acute deaths), CD (chronic deaths), and
 167 ADCD (total premature deaths; ADCD=AD+CD), estimated from linear EVA, show a decreasing
 168 trend under both scenarios. The projections indicate that compared with 2010, the reduction of AD,
 169 CD, and total deaths cases estimated based on the WHO_RR in 2049 amounted to 52%, 42%, and
 170 43%, respectively under the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario; the reduction of AD, CD, and total
 171 deaths cases estimated based on the WHO_RR in 2049 amounted to 83%, 80%, and 80%,
 172 respectively under the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario. It is worth noting that compared with 2010,
 173 the total population of China in 2030, 2040 and 2049 will decrease by 2%, 5% and 11% respectively
 174 (Figure 1). This reveals that decreases in the number of deaths associated with PM_{2.5} pollution
 175 outpaces changes in the population. In addition, the results indicate that the reductions in AD, CD,
 176 and total deaths are more significant under the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario compared to the
 177 CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario, due to stricter PM_{2.5} emission controls. For individual causes of
 178 death, AD shows a significant reduction under all scenarios, suggesting that emergency measures to

179 prevent PM_{2.5} pollution will yield substantial health benefits.

180 The PM_{2.5}-related causes of death estimated based on non-linear EVA, including LC, COPD, IHD,
181 stroke, LRI, and total deaths, all showed a small upward trend in the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE
182 scenario (Table 1 and Figure 2). Due to more aggressive pollution emission controls, the numbers
183 of deaths estimated by nonlinear EVA show a decreasing trend under the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR
184 scenario (Table 1 and Figure 2). The main reason for the different trends in causes of death under
185 the two scenarios may be related to the combination of different PM_{2.5} concentration levels and
186 distributions and development in population age distribution. As shown in Figure 1(a), compared
187 with the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario, the PM_{2.5} concentration decreases more dramatically in
188 the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario, and the corresponding PM_{2.5}-related causes of death is more
189 effectively controlled. In addition, as shown in Figure 1(b), the proportion of the population aged
190 65+ is projected to increase from 8% in 2010 to 23% in 2049, an increase of about 170 million.
191 Therefore, in the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario, there is a possibility that air quality
192 improvements in some cities have not yet reached the point of fully offsetting the health risks
193 associated with the increase in the elderly population³³, leading to a slow-growth trend in premature
194 death cases. In the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario, on the other hand, improved air quality offsets
195 the health risks associated with an increasing elderly population, contributing to a downward trend
196 in premature deaths. The projections indicate that compared with 2010, the increases in LC, COPD,
197 IHD, stroke, LRI, and total deaths cases estimated based on the nonlinear EVA in 2049 under the
198 CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario are 39%, 21%, 43%, 32%, 48%, and 28%, respectively; the
199 reduction in LC, COPD, IHD, stroke, LRI, and total deaths cases estimated based on the nonlinear
200 EVA in 2049 under the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario are 46%, 52%, 30%, 56%, 48%, and 40%,

201 respectively, compared to 2010. For specific causes of death, the number of stroke cases estimated
202 based on nonlinear EVA is the most sensitive to $PM_{2.5}$ changes under the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR
203 scenario, with the largest decrease.

204 The above causes of death estimated based on linear and nonlinear EVA show different trends in the
205 CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario. This is mainly related to the different compositions of the
206 nonlinear and linear functions themselves, together with different $PM_{2.5}$ concentration levels and
207 distributions and population age distributions, thus leading to different trends. The impact of the
208 assumption of linear or nonlinear relationships on the estimated total premature deaths related to
209 $PM_{2.5}$ is explored based on Figure 2 and Table 1. The results show that the average annual total
210 $PM_{2.5}$ -related deaths estimated from the linear EVA are higher than those from the non-linear EVA
211 in both 2010 and 2020. It may be related to the nonlinearity of the concentration-response function.
212 Some studies^{18,19} have found a non-linear relationship between air pollution and mortality, with
213 health effects increasing faster at lower concentrations than at higher concentrations. This also
214 means that linear relationships can lead to overestimates of health effects in highly polluted areas.
215 Therefore, when applying linear EVA to China with high $PM_{2.5}$ pollution in 2010 and 2020, it may
216 lead to an increase in linear estimates of premature death. The annual average total deaths related to
217 $PM_{2.5}$ from 2020 to 2049, estimated based on linear and nonlinear EVA, are approximately 2.39
218 million and 2.07 million cases under the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario; the annual average total
219 deaths related to $PM_{2.5}$ are approximately 1.46 million and 1.33 million cases under the
220 CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario. In addition, it was found that compared to the linear EVA, the
221 annual average change in $PM_{2.5}$ -related premature deaths from 2020 to 2049 under the
222 CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario, estimated based on the nonlinear EVA is projected to be -13%.

223 compared to the linear EVA; and the annual average change under the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR
 224 scenario is projected to be -9%.

225 To date, many studies have estimated PM_{2.5}-related deaths in China. For instance, Li et al. used the
 226 IER model to estimate that the number of deaths related to PM_{2.5} in mainland China in 2008 was
 227 1.14 million³³. Similarly, Wu et al. used the GEMM model to estimate that PM_{2.5}-related deaths in
 228 China in 2015 were 1.92 million³⁴. This result is comparable to the total deaths related to PM_{2.5}
 229 estimated by nonlinear EVA in this study, approximately 1.8 million cases in 2010 and 2.1 million
 230 cases in 2020, but lower than the estimates based on linear EVA. The total number of premature
 231 deaths related to PM_{2.5} in 2010 estimated by linear EVA was approximately 3.5 million as shown in
 232 Figure 2. The absolute values of the percentage change in total premature deaths estimated by EVA
 233 relative to the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario increase year by year under the CESM_SSP1-
 234 2.6_MFR scenario (Supplementary Table 1). This result is also similar to the percentage change in
 235 PM_{2.5} (Supplementary Table 1), indicating that controlling PM_{2.5} emissions helps alleviate PM_{2.5}-
 236 related diseases.

237
 238 **Figure 2. Total PM_{2.5}-related premature mortality and its percentage change relative to 2010**
 239 **in mainland China estimated with the linear EVA (RR=8.0%, recorded as WHO_RR) and**

240 **nonlinear EVA from 2010 to 2049 under different scenarios.**

241 Regarding the primary causes of death, the results of premature death cases estimated based on the
242 linear EVA model, show (Table 1) that chronic deaths is the leading cause of death under both
243 scenarios, accounting for approximately 90% of total deaths during the study period. The results
244 estimated based on nonlinear EVA (Table 1) show that ischemic heart disease is the primary cause
245 of death under both scenarios, accounting for approximately 41% to 50% of the combined total
246 deaths from the five causes (lung cancer, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, ischemic heart
247 disease, stroke, lower respiratory infections) during the study period. Similar results have been
248 reported by Liu et al.³⁵.

249 **Spatial distribution of total PM_{2.5}-related premature mortality**

250 Figures 3 and 4 show the spatial distribution of premature deaths related to PM_{2.5} in mainland China
251 from 2010 to 2049, estimated using the linear EVA (WHO_RR) and nonlinear EVA under the
252 different scenarios. Figures (a) refer to the HIST_CESM scenario in 2010, figures (b~e) represent
253 the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario during the period from 2020 to 2049, while figures (f~i) denote
254 the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario in the same period. Overall, the high values of PM_{2.5}-related
255 premature deaths are concentrated in central and eastern China (see Supplementary Figure 1 for a
256 geographic location), which accounted for about 75% of the total PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths in
257 China (Supplementary Table 2). Except for the premature deaths estimated by the nonlinear EVA
258 under the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario, the implementation of the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE and
259 CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenarios can effectively reduce PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths from 2010
260 to 2049. Calculations show that under the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE and CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR
261 scenarios, PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths are expected to decrease by up to 43% and 80% by 2049

262 compared to 2010.

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Figure 3. Spatial distribution of PM_{2.5}-related premature mortality estimated with the linear EVA (RR=8.0%, recorded as WHO_RR) in mainland China from 2010 to 2049 under different scenarios (in case). The color scale is logarithmic.

267

268

269 **Figure 4. Spatial distribution of PM_{2.5}-related premature mortality estimated with the**
 270 **nonlinear EVA in mainland China from 2010 to 2049 under different scenarios (in case). The**
 271 **color scale is logarithmic.**

272

273 Source contributions to total PM_{2.5}-related premature mortality

274 Based on the new relative risk value WHO_RR recommended by WHO, the impacts of specific
275 emission sources on premature deaths related to PM_{2.5} were investigated using the linear EVA model.
276 Figure 5 depicts the estimated premature deaths attributable to PM_{2.5} from various emission sources
277 in mainland China from 2010 to 2049 under the HIST_CESM, CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR, and
278 CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenarios, based on linear EVA (WHO_RR). The left Y-axis represents the
279 premature deaths caused by PM_{2.5} from each emission source, while the right Y-axis represents the
280 percentage change relative to 2010. Under the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario, the percentage
281 change in premature deaths caused by PM_{2.5} from the coal combustion for residential heating (re),
282 biomass burning (bi), industrial emission (in), and tailpipe emission from on-road transport (tr) in
283 mainland China in 2049 estimated with the linear EVA is projected to be -65%, -51%, -38%, and -
284 16%, respectively, relative to 2010. Under the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario, the percentage
285 change in premature deaths caused by PM_{2.5} from the coal combustion for residential heating,
286 biomass burning, industrial emission, and tailpipe emission from on-road transport in mainland
287 China in 2049 estimated with the linear EVA is projected to be -92%, -86%, -69%, and -72%,
288 respectively, relative to 2010. It is estimated that compared to the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario,
289 the implementation of more stringent scenarios from 2030 to 2049 will contribute to reducing
290 premature deaths caused by each emission source by 38% to 76%. These results indicate that
291 compared to the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario, the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario is expected
292 to effectively avoid premature deaths attributable to PM_{2.5} from various emission sources in the
293 future.

294

295 **Figure 5. Absolute contributions of anthropogenic emission sources to total PM_{2.5}-related**
 296 **premature mortality estimated with the linear EVA (RR=8.0%, recorded as WHO_RR) and**
 297 **their percentage change relative to 2010 in mainland China under different scenarios from**
 298 **2010 to 2049.**

299 Supplementary Figure 2 shows the relative contribution of various emission sources in mainland
 300 China to the PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths estimated using linear EVA for the period 2010-2049
 301 under different scenarios. Regarding the average annual contribution levels of emission sources for
 302 the period 2020~2049, the results indicate that the biomass burning (40%) and industrial (34%)
 303 emission sources are the main contributors to PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths estimated using linear
 304 EVA under all scenarios. Therefore, the health benefits or risks associated with reductions in PM_{2.5}
 305 exposure under the scenarios assuming implementation of PM_{2.5} emission controls are primarily
 306 from biomass burning and industrial emissions. Moreover, the changes in emission source-driven
 307 PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths estimated using the linear EVA (WHO_RR) model for the period
 308 2010~2049 are shown in Figure 6. The PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths in 2010 and 2049 refer to
 309 the sum of PM_{2.5}-induced premature deaths from the coal combustion for residential heating,
 310 biomass burning, industrial emission, and tailpipe emission from on-road transport in the

311 corresponding years. The results indicate that, under all scenarios, the primary contributor to the
312 reduction in PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths from 2010 to 2049 is the biomass burning source.
313 Specifically, the predicted results are as follows: under the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE and
314 CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenarios, PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths from the coal combustion for
315 residential heating, biomass burning, industrial emission, and tailpipe emission from on-road
316 transport are expected to decrease by 0.86 million and 1.55 million cases from 2010 to 2049, with
317 54% and 51% of these reductions attributable to the control of biomass burning source emissions in
318 the corresponding scenarios. Furthermore, as indicated by the results in Figure 2, the total PM_{2.5}-
319 related premature deaths under the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE and CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenarios
320 are projected to decrease by 1.47 million and 2.76 million cases from 2010 to 2049. This
321 demonstrates that the reduction in overall PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths during the study period is
322 not solely due to the emission control of the four sources mentioned above. These findings suggest
323 that, in addition to focusing on PM_{2.5} emissions from the coal combustion for residential heating,
324 biomass burning, industrial emission, and tailpipe emission from on-road transport, future research
325 should also consider other sources of emissions not covered in this work, such as other
326 anthropogenic and natural emissions.

327

328 **Figure 6. The inter-annual variations of anthropogenic-driven total PM_{2.5}-related premature**
 329 **mortality estimated with the linear EVA (RR=8.0%, recorded as WHO_RR) under different**
 330 **scenarios in mainland China.**

331 Discussion

332 We propose to synthesize the linear or nonlinear relationship between PM_{2.5} concentrations and
 333 mortality and give a more comprehensive projection of future premature deaths. Based on the
 334 DEHM model, we designed sensitivity experiments to capture PM_{2.5} pollution in various Chinese
 335 cities under different emission reduction scenarios in the future. By assuming linearity and
 336 nonlinearity between PM_{2.5} concentration and mortality in the EVA model, we found that the linear
 337 and nonlinear relationship between the two has less impact on the results of health impact
 338 assessment. The annual mean change in total PM_{2.5}-related mortality estimated from the linear and
 339 nonlinear relationships ranged from 9% to 13% under both scenarios. This is also largely attributable
 340 to China's aging population. Our projections indicate that the proportion of the population over 65
 341 years of age is projected to increase from 8% in 2010 to 23% in 2049, an increase of about 170
 342 million. This proportion plays an important role in the linear and nonlinear relationship. It is worth
 343 noting that population aging is also an important challenge for China to deal with air pollution in

344 the future³⁶. More attention should be paid to aging in the future.

345 The results of the health impact assessment indicate that strict pollution emission controls on
346 anthropogenic sources are an effective way to significantly alleviate the PM_{2.5}-related mortality
347 burden. Compared to the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario, implementing more stringent
348 hypothetical scenarios during 2030-2049 will help reduce premature deaths from PM_{2.5} emissions
349 across various sources by 38% to 76%. Using linear EVA estimates, the implementation of the
350 CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE and CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenarios from 2010 to 2049 would avoid 0.86
351 million and 1.55 million PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths from the coal combustion for residential
352 heating, biomass burning, industry, and tailpipe emission from on-road transport, with
353 approximately 54% and 51% achieved through controlling biomass burning source emissions in the
354 corresponding scenarios. Therefore, there is an urgent need for China to implement further measures
355 to effectively reduce biomass burning emissions. The relevant study³⁷ has proposed that the use of
356 advanced stoves, such as gasified biomass cooking stoves for biomass and “under-fire” heating
357 stoves for a variety of solid fuels, can reduce pollutant emissions from domestic coal and biomass
358 combustion by improving combustion and thermal efficiency. Improving solid fuel quality, such as
359 including fuel volatile matter content, fuel size and fuel form, is also one of the possible ways to
360 reduce pollutant emissions from domestic coal and biomass burning³⁷. In addition, China should,
361 on the one hand, continue or intensify the comprehensive utilization of straw and the ban on burning
362 (from the Action Plan for Sustained Improvement of Air Quality³⁸) to reduce biomass burning
363 emissions and the health burden caused by air pollution. On the other hand, potential emerging
364 technologies, including energy storage technologies, should be developed. For example, the
365 deployment of heat storage devices (e.g., large-scale water heat storage tanks) in centralized biomass

366 heating systems is encouraged to balance heating demand and fuel supply to avoid high pollution
367 from peak combustion; and the efficiency of biomass gasification to hydrogen or liquefied fuels can
368 be enhanced through energy storage technologies to reduce carbon emissions from traditional fuel
369 production processes.

370 This study benefited from having data on PM_{2.5} concentrations from various anthropogenic emission
371 sources spanning 30 years and based on EVA model to synergistically consider the linear or non-
372 linear relationship between PM_{2.5} concentrations and mortality. The aim is to fully reveal the health
373 benefits of future emission reduction measures. However, uncertainties may arise due to
374 uncertainties in the exposure-response-functions, the incomplete consideration of species in the
375 health impact assessment and the incomplete inclusion of emission sources and uncertainties in
376 emissions in the DEHM model applied to China.

377 Regarding the health impact assessment, the current EVA system considers the following
378 compounds related to human health impacts: O₃, NO₂, SO₂, SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺, primary emissions
379 of PM_{2.5}. and secondary organic aerosols (SOA)³⁹. For the secondary inorganic components, the full
380 weight of the particles including nitrate, sulphate and ammonium is applied as follows: Besides
381 SO₄²⁻ the full weight of H₂SO₄, NH₄SO₄ and (NH₄)₂SO₄ are included. The same applies for NO₃⁻
382 where also NH₄NO₃ is included³⁹. Primary particles include dust, elemental carbon (both fresh and
383 aged), organic matter (OM) and sea salt³⁹. Regarding baseline mortality data selection, using 2017
384 baseline mortality data for future scenario projections could affect future changes in premature
385 mortality associated with PM_{2.5}. Nonetheless, this study considered changes in population and PM_{2.5}
386 concentrations under future scenarios, which reduces uncertainty in the results of future health
387 impact assessments. It is important to note that, while the linear or nonlinear exposure-response

388 relationships between PM_{2.5} concentrations and health burdens may introduce uncertainties, the
389 strength of this study lies in its simultaneous evaluation of health burdens estimated based on both
390 linear and nonlinear relationships. This comprehensive approach allows for a thorough assessment
391 of the maximum anticipated health benefits from the implementation of the hypothetical scenarios
392 in mainland China. Specifically, for the cases discussed in this paper, the upper limit of health
393 benefits for the period 2010 to 2049 is estimated to potentially avoid approximately 2.76 million
394 PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths in mainland China (Figure 2), annually. Regarding the predicted
395 PM_{2.5} concentrations, a rather low resolution could add to the uncertainty of the exposure. Moreover,
396 the DEHM model does not include all PM_{2.5} emission sources, such as wind blown dust/sand
397 emissions, which are predominantly concentrated in western China⁴⁰. This omission could lead to
398 an underestimation of predicted concentrations, however, since these are natural emissions, it will
399 not influence the scenarios. Since the major PM_{2.5} pollution and population in mainland China are
400 mainly concentrated in the central-eastern region of China, the number of premature deaths is also
401 in these regions, consistent with the findings of this study and Li et al.⁴¹. Given the focus of this
402 study on the impacts of anthropogenic emission sources (coal combustion for residential heating,
403 biomass burning, industrial emission, and tailpipe emission from on-road transport) on PM_{2.5}-related
404 premature deaths, the impact of dust emissions was not considered. To justify this omissions,
405 previous study results^{34,35} were compared in “*Health burden analysis*”: the total PM_{2.5}-related deaths
406 estimated using the nonlinear EVA in this study are comparable to those of Wu et al.³⁴, with a
407 maximum difference of 11%, indicating that the impact of excluding dust emissions is within an
408 acceptable range. In the DEHM model, the transportation source only considers tailpipe emissions
409 from road transport, excluding non-tailpipe emissions from vehicles like road dust, brake dust, and

410 tire wear, as well as other transportation sources like ships and airplanes. This is because tailpipe
411 emissions from road transport have a more significant impact on air quality and its associated health
412 risks than emissions from other transportation sources like ships and airplanes⁴²⁻⁴⁵. Similarly,
413 comparisons with the existing literature were made to reveal the plausibility of this study's
414 assessment of the impact of tailpipe emission from on-road transport: Zheng et al.⁴⁶ assessed the
415 contribution of sources of PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths in China and showed that the contribution
416 of vehicle emissions to the premature deaths due to PM_{2.5} pollution increased from 8% in 2005 to
417 14% in 2015, which is similar to the results of this study. The contribution of tailpipe emission from
418 on-road transport to PM_{2.5}-related premature mortality ranges from 14% to 23% from 2010 to 2049
419 under the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE and CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenarios in this study
420 (Supplementary Figure 2). Among them, the contribution of tailpipe emissions from on-road
421 transport was 14% in 2010. Therefore, the contribution of tailpipe emissions from on-road transport
422 to PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths in this study can be considered reasonable. In conclusion, the
423 methodology employed in this study is reliable for estimating current and future PM_{2.5}-related
424 premature deaths, assessing the health benefits of pollutant abatement measures, and identifying the
425 specific contributions of various anthropogenic emission sources. This approach also provides a
426 reference for future studies aiming to estimate environmental and health benefits under different
427 PM_{2.5} control scenarios in different countries and regions. Future research will further consider a
428 broader range of species and sources on health impacts, enhance the resolution of the DEHM model,
429 and propose scenarios and criteria for determining the applicability of linear and nonlinear models
430 to accurately predict future PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths.

431

432 **Methods**

433 Meteorological data and emission inventories

434 Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) includes a historical period covering the
435 years 1850–2014, and a future period from 2015 to 2100, providing an important data foundation
436 for assessing models' ability to simulate past and current climate change and for projecting future
437 climate change^{47,48}. Wang et al.³¹ also adopted the above rules, dividing 1950–2014 into the
438 historical period and 2015–2100 into the future period. Accordingly, this study adheres to the CMIP6
439 division between historical and future periods, considering the historical years of 2010–2014, as well
440 as future years of 2020 (near-term), 2030 (mid-term), 2040, and 2049 (long-term). From a temporal
441 perspective, we investigate the trends of PM_{2.5} concentrations and its resulting health burden in
442 China during the future period. The meteorological data used as input to the DEHM model, is
443 obtained from the numerical weather prediction model WRFv4.1⁴⁹ and driven by global reanalysis
444 or global climate simulation. For 2010–2014, WRF is driven by global meteorological data obtained
445 from the ERA5 dataset and the Community Earth System Model (CESM) global model, respectively.
446 Notably, CESM is one of the models participating in CMIP6. In this study, based on SSP2-4.5 and
447 SSP1-2.6 of the shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs), we utilized the CESM to simulate and
448 predict future climates in China from 2020 to 2049 under two scenarios: CESM_SSP2-4.5 and
449 CESM_SSP1-2.6. Specifically, the SSP2-4.5 scenario represents a moderate radiative forcing
450 scenario that continues the historical development pattern throughout the 21st century, with radiative
451 forcing stabilizing at 4.5 W/m² by 2100³¹. As for the SSP1-2.6 scenario, a relatively optimistic trend
452 in human development, characterized by substantial investments in education and health, robust
453 economic growth, and well-functioning organizational operations are assumed. This scenario is

454 progressively transitioning towards sustainability-related measures, with radiative forcing
455 stabilizing at 2.6 W/m^2 by 2100³¹. In addition, there are some differences between the two scenarios
456 described above in terms of urbanization projections and assumptions about economic
457 decarbonization. For example, in the urbanization projections: the SSP1-2.6 scenario assumes rapid
458 urbanization in all country groups associated with high income growth⁵⁰. The SSP2-4.5 scenario
459 assumes a moderate rate of urbanization growth around the world compared to the historical
460 experience of similar countries⁵⁰. In terms of scenarios for decarbonizing the economy: SSP1-2.6
461 scenario assumes that economic growth is decoupled from energy demand through improved energy
462 efficiency and increased use of renewable energy⁵¹. The scenario features low social acceptability
463 of other conventional technologies (such as fossil fuel conversion technologies, nuclear power, and
464 carbon dioxide capture and storage) except non-biomass renewables, which also feature fast
465 technological improvements⁵¹. In addition, the adoption of carbon dioxide capture and storage in
466 the power sector will have an impact on future $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ emissions from this sector. The SSP2-4.5
467 scenario generally assumes that all technologies develop and are socially acceptable at medium
468 levels⁵¹. All CMIP6_CESM results can be obtained from the official CMIP6 archive ([https://esgf-
469 node.llnl.gov/search/cmip6/](https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/cmip6/)).

470 The emission inventory is obtained from Eclipse v6b⁵². The future emission projections in this
471 dataset are based on explicit assumptions about economic development and the effectiveness of
472 specific emission control policies. The Eclipse v6b dataset offers two emission reduction scenarios,
473 both of which were utilized in this study: the Current Legislation Emission Scenario (CLE) and
474 Maximum Feasible Reductions (MFR). The CLE scenario is applied throughout the study period,
475 encompassing both historical and future periods. It is based on the assumption that future emission

476 levels will continue to adhere to existing laws and policies, without additional emission reduction
477 measures. The MFR scenario is applied in the future period, considering the maximum achievable
478 emission reduction under existing technological and economic conditions. This implies the
479 implementation of all feasible emission reduction measures, both technically and economically
480 viable, to achieve the greatest reduction in emissions.

481 In this study, four scenarios were designed to investigate the impact of different policy assumptions
482 on PM_{2.5} concentration and health burdens associated with PM_{2.5} exposure in historical and future
483 periods in China (see Figure 7 for the overview): (1) HIST_CESM: Historical runs (2010–2014)
484 based on CESM_HIST meteorological data and Eclipse_CLE emission assumptions, considered as
485 the baseline scenario. (2) HIST_ERA5: Historical runs (2010–2014) based on ERA5 meteorological
486 data and Eclipse_CLE emission assumptions, used to assess the data quality of CESM for simulating
487 Chinese climate. (3) CESM_SSP2–4.5_CLE: Future runs (2020, 2030, 2040, and 2049) based on
488 CESM_SSP2–4.5 meteorological data and Eclipse_CLE emission assumptions. This scenario is
489 considered to align with the implementation of future emission reduction strategies in China. (4)
490 CESM_SSP1–2.6_MFR: Future runs (2020, 2030, 2040, and 2049) based on CESM_SSP1–2.6
491 meteorological data and Eclipse_MFR emission assumptions. This scenario is regarded as an
492 optimistic assumption for emission reduction.

493

494 **Figure 7. Emission inventory and meteorological conditions in four simulation scenarios.**495 **Setup of the DEHM Model**

496 A significant number of studies have shown that the DEHM can well capture many features of PM
497 and its precursors' changes in large-scale space and exhibits good performance⁵³. DEHM is also part
498 of the 11 model ensemble in the European Copernicus Atmospheric Service and is continuously
499 evaluated as part of this service (<https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu>). This study applies DEHM to
500 predict and assess PM_{2.5} concentrations in a future context. A two-way nested domain⁵⁴ of the
501 DEHM model system is used in this study. A mother domain with a resolution of 150 km × 150 km
502 is employed on a polar stereographic projection, true at 60°N to cover the entire Northern
503 Hemisphere to account for intercontinental transport. The nested domain covered the whole China
504 consisting of 150 × 150 grid cells with a resolution of 50 km × 50 km. Vertically, there are 29
505 unevenly distributed layers, with the highest level reaching 100 hPa, and the lowest layer is
506 approximately 20 m in height. The time resolution of the DEHM model output is one hour. The
507 meteorological fields are simulated using the WRFv4.1⁴⁹ setup with exactly same domain setup as
508 the DEHM model. The WRF model is hence used to dynamic downscaling the global data. For the
509 historical weather and climate, WRF is driven by ERA5 and CESM_HIST, while CESM_SSP2-4.5

510 and CESM_SSP1-2.6 is used for the future climate. The gas-phase chemistry module included 66
511 species, 9 primary particles (including natural particles such as sea salt), and 138 chemical
512 reactions⁵³. The SOA are calculated using the volatility basis set (see details in Im et al.⁵⁵). In
513 addition to the anthropogenic emissions, DEHM also includes emissions from biogenic emissions,
514 such as vegetation, sea salt, lightning, soil, etc. The current version of the DEHM model does not
515 include wind-blown, resuspended dust emissions or resuspended road dust.

516 In this study, the DEHM model uses anthropogenic emissions from Eclipse v6b and biogenic
517 emissions are calculated online using the Model of Emissions of Gases and Aerosols from Nature
518 (MEGAN) (see details in Zare et al.⁵⁶ and Im et al.⁵⁵).

519 Anthropogenic emission sources and their sensitivity experiments design

520 The reviews^{20,21} mentioned above show that coal combustion, biomass burning, transportation, and
521 industrial sources are the major anthropogenic emission sources in most parts of China. We
522 conducted sensitivity experiments targeting these four sources to quantitatively assess their
523 contributions to PM_{2.5} concentration and PM_{2.5}-related health burdens under different scenarios (see
524 Figure 8). In this study, the coal combustion refers to coal heating from the residential sector.
525 Biomass burning includes open burning of agricultural biomass, domestic biomass burning for
526 cooking and heating, and biomass burning from biomass power plants and coal-fired power plants,
527 which includes co-firing of biomass and coal. To accelerate carbon reduction in coal-fired power
528 generation, the Chinese government has issued a series of policies supporting and encouraging the
529 coupling of coal and biomass for power generation⁵⁷. This undoubtedly adds complexity to
530 distinguishing between PM_{2.5} emissions from coal combustion and biomass fuel. Furthermore,
531 biomass is a renewable energy source with abundant resources and various forms of utilization. Its

532 effective utilization is expected to help alleviate the global energy shortage and climate change
533 caused by the massive use of fossil fuels. China has taken a series of measures to cope with climate
534 change, the conflict between energy supply and demand, and to protect the ecological environment.
535 Driven by the energy strategy, the scale of biomass utilization and biomass power generation
536 industry in China has been expanding⁵⁸. Considering the aforementioned reasons, we include PM_{2.5}
537 emissions from coal-fired power plants in our analysis. Industry source is primarily from specific
538 industry processes. It is worth noting that in the DEHM model, the transportation source only
539 considers tailpipe emissions from on-road transport, excluding non-tailpipe emissions from vehicles
540 like road dust, brake dust, and tire wear, as well as other transportation sources like ships and
541 airplanes.

542 These sensitivity experiments were carried out within the four scenarios proposed in Figure 7,
543 including both the non-perturbation condition (referred to as the NPC case) and perturbation
544 condition (referred to as the PC case), and a total of 50 runs were performed. Under the non-
545 perturbation condition, all aforementioned emission sources were considered. Under the
546 perturbation condition, reduction designs were implemented for emissions from coal combustion,
547 biomass burning, industrial sources, and tailpipe emission from on-road transport. The emission
548 from each individual source is reduced by 30%. The choice of 30 % was motivated by the
549 consideration that the perturbation would be large enough to produce a sizeable impact (i.e., more
550 than numerical noise) even at long distances, while small enough to be in the near-linear atmospheric
551 chemistry regime^{59,60}. The implementation steps are as follows:

552 Firstly, in order to estimate PM_{2.5} concentrations from coal combustion for residential heating and
553 biomass burning, this study obtained the percentage contributions of PM_{2.5} emissions from coal

554 combustion for residential heating, domestic biomass burning for cooking and heating to PM_{2.5}
 555 emissions of the residential sector, respectively, as well as the percentage contributions of PM_{2.5}
 556 emissions from biomass combustion in power plants to the total PM_{2.5} emissions from the power
 557 sector, through data collection and calculation.

558 Then, on this basis, a uniform 30% emission reduction control was applied to the coal combustion
 559 for residential heating, biomass burning (including open burning of agricultural biomass, domestic
 560 biomass burning for cooking and heating, and biomass burning from biomass power plants and coal-
 561 fired power plants), industrial sources, and tailpipe emission from on-road transport studied in this
 562 study.

563 Subsequently, the final percentage reduction was obtained, as shown in Figure 8. Under the
 564 perturbation condition for residential heating coal combustion, 8% emission reduction control was
 565 applied to the residential sector; under the perturbation condition for biomass burning, 21%, 30%,
 566 and 16% emission reduction control was applied to the residential sector, the agricultural sector, and
 567 the energy sector, respectively; under the perturbation condition for the industry source, 30%
 568 emission reduction control was applied to the industry sector; and under the perturbation condition
 569 for the tailpipe emission from on-road transport, 30% emission reduction control was applied to the
 570 tailpipe emission from on-road transport.

571 Finally, the PM_{2.5} concentration for each sector is calculated using Equations (1~3):

$$C_{P,i} = \frac{C_{NPC,i} - C_{PC,i}}{30\%} \quad (1)$$

$$C_{P,primary\ PM2.5} = C_{P,total\ PM2.5} - C_{P,SIA} - C_{P,SOA} \quad (2)$$

$$C_{secondary} = C_{NPC,SOA} + C_{NPC,SIA} \quad (3)$$

572 where, *i* refers to the type of pollutants, i.e., total PM_{2.5}, SOA, secondary inorganic aerosols, and

573 primary $PM_{2.5}$. $C_{NPC,i}$ represents concentrations of the pollutant i in the NPC case. $C_{PC,i}$ represents
 574 concentrations of the pollutant i in the PC case. $C_{P,i}$ represents concentrations of the pollutant i by
 575 the specific emission sector P which is perturbed (perturbation sectors P include coal combustion
 576 for residential heating, biomass burning, industry sources, tailpipe emission from on-road transport).
 577 $C_{P,primary PM_{2.5}}$ represents concentrations of primary $PM_{2.5}$ by the perturbation sectors P.
 578 $C_{secondary}$ represents $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations by the secondary aerosol formation.

579

580 **Figure 8. Emission reduction design for anthropogenic emission sources; a) was obtained from**
 581 **the literature⁶¹, b) were obtained from the literature^{58,61-67}.**

582 Population and baseline mortality data

583 Population density data has been taken from the Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center⁶⁸ on
 584 a 30 arc-minute spatial resolution, which was subsequently aggregated to the 50 km × 50 km
 585 resolution in the nested model domain of DEHM. The dataset includes global population estimates
 586 by age and sex for 2010, expressed as counts (number of people per pixel) and densities (number of
 587 people per square kilometer), consistent with national censuses and population registers⁶⁸. The
 588 dataset is categorized by age into five-year age groups from ages 0-4 to ages 85+⁶⁸. In these data,
 589 the age breakdown is only available for 2010. Therefore, the age distribution data for China from

590 World Population Prospects⁶⁹ for 1950-2049 were used to process the population data from the
591 Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center to obtain age distributions for all other years. The age
592 distribution data were initially spaced at 5-year intervals and subsequently processed to the actual
593 years in the EVA by interpolation (see details in Im et al.¹⁴). Considering that the number of
594 premature deaths attributable to PM_{2.5} as a proportion of the total population is minimal, and to
595 facilitate comparison of the effect of reduced PM_{2.5} emissions on total premature deaths attributable
596 to PM_{2.5}, the same population structure is used for the SSP2-4.5 and SSP1-2.6 scenarios. The
597 country-specific baseline mortality for each age group was obtained from Global Burden of
598 Disease⁷⁰. Due to the lack of data on future baseline mortality, this study used 2017 baseline
599 mortality for future scenario projections.

600 EVA model and its sensitivity experiments design

601 The EVA model^{71,72} is based on the impact-pathway chain methodology⁷³. As a health impact
602 assessment system, it has been widely applied^{14,39,55,71,72,74,75}. Combining calculated air pollutant
603 concentrations with population data, we can calculate human exposure, health effects (morbidity
604 and mortality), and associated external costs⁷⁵. This work focuses on premature mortality. With
605 updates to the EVA model, it is possible to calculate premature deaths due to exposure to air
606 pollutants (including PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO₂, and O₃) using linear ERFs, as well as cause-specific mortality
607 using nonlinear functions based on Burnett et al.⁷⁶.

608 The linear version of the EVA model (referred to as linear EVA) calculates the health burden using
609 ERFs based on a relative risk of 8.0% for all-cause chronic mortality due to PM_{2.5} based on a review
610 by Chen and Hoek⁷⁷, as recently recommended by the WHO⁷⁸ (denoted as WHO_RR). The
611 nonlinear version of the EVA model (referred to as nonlinear EVA) incorporates nonlinear, location

612 specific functions to estimate cause-specific mortality attributable to $PM_{2.5}$ ¹⁴. This version employs
 613 the GEMM model to calculate relative risks (RR) using hazard ratio functions⁷⁶. In the present study,
 614 the methodology of Burnett et al.⁷⁶ as implemented in Lelieveld et al.⁷⁹ for $PM_{2.5}$ -related mortality
 615 was followed for estimating the RR as:

$$RR = \exp \left\{ \theta \frac{\log \left[\left(\frac{z}{\alpha} \right) + 1 \right]}{\left(1 + \exp \left\{ -\frac{(z - \mu)}{\nu} \right\} \right)} \right\} \quad (4)$$

616 where $z = \max(0, PM_{2.5} - 2.4 \mu g m^{-3})$, and θ , α , μ and ν are variables obtained from Burnett et al.⁷⁶
 617 and z is the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration. \log is here the natural logarithmic function. The GEMM model
 618 adopted in the EVA assumes a cut-off $PM_{2.5}$ concentration of $2.4 \mu g m^{-3}$ ⁷⁶. The linear EVA assumes
 619 a straight-line relationship between $PM_{2.5}$ concentration and mortality risk, meaning that the risk
 620 increases proportionally with increasing $PM_{2.5}$ levels. In contrast, the nonlinear EVA uses more
 621 complex that allow for a non-proportional change in risk, with a steeper increase in the impacts at
 622 lower concentrations than at higher concentrations^{18,19}. For more detailed descriptions of the linear
 623 EVA, nonlinear EVA, and GEMM models, please refer to previous publications^{14,39,55,71,72,74-76}.
 624 In this study, atmospheric $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations under specific scenarios (CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE,
 625 CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR) simulated by the DEHM model, including overall $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations or
 626 $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations due to specific anthropogenic emission sources (coal combustion for
 627 residential heating, biomass burning, tailpipe emission from on-road transport, and industrial
 628 sources), as well as projected population data are used as input data to the EVA model to estimate
 629 health burdens associated with $PM_{2.5}$ pollution exposures or the effects of specific anthropogenic
 630 emission sources on the health burdens associated with them. The study focuses on the following
 631 health burdens (as shown in Table 2): the linear EVA was used to estimate premature deaths

632 attributable to $PM_{2.5}$ exposure, including acute deaths due to short-term $PM_{2.5}$ exposure (AD),
 633 chronic deaths due to long-term $PM_{2.5}$ exposure (CD), and total deaths due to $PM_{2.5}$ exposure
 634 ($ADCD=AD+CD$). Additionally, the nonlinear EVA model was used to estimate five specific causes
 635 of death: lung cancer (LC), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), ischemic heart disease
 636 (IHD), and stroke – all four regarded as non-communicable diseases (NCD), as well as lower
 637 respiratory infections (LRI), together giving a total number of premature deaths attributable to $PM_{2.5}$
 638 exposure.

639 **Table 2. The causes of premature deaths attributable to $PM_{2.5}$ exposure explored in this study**

Model	Premature deaths
Linear EVA	Acute Deaths (AD)
	Chronic Deaths (CD)
	Total premature deaths ($ADCD=AD+CD$)
Nonlinear EVA	Lung Cancer (LC)
	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)
	Ischemic Heart Disease (IHD)
	Stroke
	Lower Respiratory Infections (LRI)
	Non-Communicable Diseases ($NCD=LC+COPD+IHD+stroke$)
Total premature deaths ($=NCD+LRI$)	

640 Note: For a detailed description of the method part, i.e., meteorological data and emission
 641 inventories, the simulation scenarios, DEHM model setup, and model evaluation, please refer to the
 642 previous publication³² if the readers are interested.

643

644 **Data availability**

645 All CMIP6_CESM results can be obtained at <https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/cmip6/>. The emission

646 inventory can be obtained at

647 https://previous.iiasa.ac.at/web/home/research/researchPrograms/air/Global_emissions.html.

648 Population density data can be obtained at <https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/data/collection/gpw->

649 [v4/sets/browse](https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/data/collection/gpw-v4/sets/browse). Other data are available from the corresponding author upon request.

650

651

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841 **Figure legends**

842 **Figure 1. Projection of annual average PM_{2.5} concentration population sizes and age**
 843 **distributions in China from 2010 to 2049.** Subplots show the projection of annual average PM_{2.5}
 844 concentration and population sizes (a), and age distributions (b) in China from 2010 to 2049. Purple
 845 bars and red and green triangles (a) represent population size; black and orange line graphs (a)
 846 represent PM_{2.5} concentrations under CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE and CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenarios,
 847 respectively. Blue, yellow, purple, green, and orange rectangles (b) represent the age distributions
 848 in 2049, 2040, 2030, 2020, and 2010, respectively.

849 **Figure 2. Total PM_{2.5}-related premature mortality and its percentage change relative to 2010**
 850 **in mainland China estimated with the linear EVA (RR=8.0%, recorded as WHO_RR) and**
 851 **nonlinear EVA from 2010 to 2049 under different scenarios.** Three zones from left to right
 852 represent HIST_CESM, CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE, and CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenarios. Blue and
 853 orange bars represent the total PM_{2.5}-related premature mortality estimated by linear and nonlinear
 854 EVA. Red and black line plots represent the percent change estimated by linear and nonlinear EVA.

855 **Figure 3. Spatial distribution of PM_{2.5}-related premature mortality estimated with the linear**
 856 **EVA (RR=8.0%, recorded as WHO_RR) in mainland China from 2010 to 2049 under different**
 857 **scenarios (in case). The color scale is logarithmic.** (a) refer to the HIST_CESM scenario in 2010,
 858 (b~e) represent the CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario during the period from 2020 to 2049, while (f~i)
 859 denote the CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario in the same period.

860 **Figure 4. Spatial distribution of PM_{2.5}-related premature mortality estimated with the**
 861 **nonlinear EVA in mainland China from 2010 to 2049 under different scenarios (in case). The**
 862 **color scale is logarithmic.** (a) refer to the HIST_CESM scenario in 2010, (b~e) represent the
 863 CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE scenario during the period from 2020 to 2049, while (f~i) denote the
 864 CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR scenario in the same period.

865 **Figure 5. Absolute contributions of anthropogenic emission sources to total PM_{2.5}-related**
 866 **premature mortality estimated with the linear EVA (RR=8.0%, recorded as WHO_RR) and**
 867 **their percentage change relative to 2010 in mainland China under different scenarios from**
 868 **2010 to 2049.** Anthropogenic emission sources include coal combustion for residential heating (re),

869 biomass burning (bi), industry (in), and tailpipe emission from on-road transport (tr). Three zones
 870 from left to right represent HIST_CESM, CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE, and CESM_SSP1-2.6_MFR
 871 scenarios. Dark blue, light blue, orange, and red rectangles represent the absolute contributions of
 872 tailpipe emission from on-road transport (tr), industry (in), biomass burning (bi), and coal
 873 combustion for residential heating (re) to total PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths, respectively. Green,
 874 orange, red, and black line plots represent the contribution of tailpipe emission from on-road
 875 transport, industry, biomass burning, and coal combustion for residential heating to the percentage
 876 change, respectively.

877 **Figure 6. The inter-annual variations of anthropogenic-driven total PM_{2.5}-related premature**
 878 **mortality estimated with the linear EVA (RR=8.0%, recorded as WHO_RR) under different**
 879 **scenarios in mainland China.** Dark blue, light blue, orange, and red rectangles represent the inter-
 880 annual variations of total PM_{2.5}-related premature mortality driven by tailpipe emission from on-
 881 road transport (tr), industry (in), biomass burning (bi), and coal combustion for residential heating
 882 (re), respectively. Two zones from left to right represent CESM_SSP2-4.5_CLE, and CESM_SSP1-
 883 2.6_MFR scenarios. PM_{2.5}-related premature deaths in 2010 and 2049 refer to the sum of PM_{2.5}-
 884 induced premature deaths from re, bi, in, and tr sources in the corresponding years.

885 **Figure 7. Emission inventory and meteorological conditions in four simulation scenarios.**

886 **Figure 8. Emission reduction design for anthropogenic emission sources; a) was obtained from**
 887 **the literature⁶¹, b) were obtained from the literature^{58,61-67}.** SNAP, the acronym for Selected Air
 888 Pollution Nomenclature, was developed by the EMEP/EEA (Guidelines for Air Pollutant Emission
 889 Inventories) project in synchronization with the IPCC/OECD (Integrated Pollution Prevention and
 890 Control) nomenclature for source categories of emitting activities
 891 (https://en.eustat.eus/documentos/elem_13173/definicion.html).

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921 Contributions

922 Liu, J. and Im, U. conceived the study. Brandt, J. performed EVA simulations. Liu, J., Christensen,

923 J.H., Ye, Z. and Im, U. performed DEHM simulations. Liu, J. and Chen, T. processed and analyzed

924 data. Liu, J. prepared main figures and drafted paper. Brandt, J., Christensen, J.H., Ye, Z., Chen, T.,

925 Dong, S., Geels, C., Yuan, Y., Nenes, A. and Im, U. contributed to the interpretation of findings,

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929 **Ethics declarations**

930 Competing interests

931 The authors declare no competing interests.

932 **Supplementary information**

933 Geographic location of eastern, central, western and north-eastern China (Supplementary Figure 1),

934 the percentage contributions of anthropogenic emission sources to total PM_{2.5}-related premature

935 mortality estimated with the linear EVA from 2010 to 2049 under different scenarios in mainland

936 China (Supplementary Figure 2), the impact of emission reduction scenarios on the number of

937 premature deaths attributed $PM_{2.5}$ concentration in mainland China from 2010 to 2049
938 (Supplementary Table 1) and percentage of $PM_{2.5}$ -related premature deaths in China by region in
939 relation to total $PM_{2.5}$ -related premature deaths in China (Supplementary Table 2) are provided in
940 the Supplementary Materials file.
941